

Modeling The Thermodynamic Characteristics of Benzenoid Hydrocarbons Using R Topological Indices

Kerem Yamaç

Faculty of Education, Van Yüzüncü Yıl University, Türkiye

kyamac@yyu.edu.tr

ABSTRACT

QSPR modeling uses modern mathematical techniques to forecast the properties of compounds based on their chemical structures. Graphical indices are mathematical methods that efficiently correlate the physicochemical, thermodynamic, and biological aspects of materials. This research examines benzenoid hydrocarbons (BHs) and assesses the effectiveness of R molecular topological indices in predicting the chemical properties of BHs. Our statistical analysis indicates strong performance with a correlation coefficient over 0.97, meeting the minimum requirement for comparative testing. Our statistical research shows that R topological indices outperform them in predicting the chemical properties of BHs. The results indicate that they can be further utilized in QSPR modeling. Our research plays a crucial role in combating the spread of visual indicators.

Keywords: QSPR, Benzenoid hydrocarbons, R topological indices.

1. INTRODUCTION

Contemporary chemistry uses correlation and regression models in QSPR research to relate a compound's physicochemical, thermodynamic, and quantum-theoretic features to its molecular structure. The origins of this subject may be traced back to a significant study by Harold Wiener in 1947, where he introduced the concept of the path number, which was later termed the Wiener index. This index is defined as the total sum of distances between all possible pairs of vertices in a graph. Harold Wiener¹ demonstrated a substantial correlation between the path number and the boiling point of alkanes. The study of graphical molecular descriptors began at that point. A graphical index is a consistent number that converts a chemical structure into a hydrogen-depleted chemical graph, resulting in a mathematical real number. Chemical

graph theory deals with organic structures by converting a molecule into its chemical graph. This graph is created by a one-to-one relationship between atoms and vertices, and bonds and edges. Topological descriptors are used to create regression models to accurately predict various physicochemical properties such as enthalpies of sublimation, formation, combustion, and vaporization², normal boiling points³, and thermodynamic characteristics⁴ like entropy (S^0) and heat capacity (C_p) of hydrocarbons and organic structures.

Research on computational analysis of graphical indices for various chemical and nanostructures is now ongoing. Zaman et al.⁵ calculated specific degree-based graphical indices for cerium oxide nanostructures. Hayat & Imran⁶ examined the topological characteristics of carbon nanocones $CNC_k[n]$ using degree-based indices. Arockiaraj et al.⁷ computed hybrid geometric harmonic-Zagreb degree-based descriptors for specific polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons (PAHs) and assessed their effectiveness in QSPR investigations. Paul and colleagues⁸ performed a comparative examination of multiplicative and scalar multiplicative degree-based indices to assess their potential in structure-property modeling. Chu et al.⁹ calculated Zagreb-related polynomials and indices for benzenoid triangular and hourglass systems. Rauf et al.¹⁰ utilized edge-weighted and degree-based entropy in the modeling of structure-property relationships in benzenoid hydrocarbons. For further computational analysis of graph-theoretic topological indices of chemical structures, please consult references¹¹⁻²¹.

Graphical indices are categorized into many types such as valency descriptors²² counting-based descriptors²³, distance-based indices²⁴, and spectral descriptors²⁵ depending on their definitions and structures. Many graphical indicators have been proposed^{26,27} and their number is increasing daily. Avoiding the emergence of new descriptors by not adhering to any established criteria. Most of the inefficient descriptors identified so far are graph-theoretic. Gutman & Tošović²⁸ mentioned that there is a lack of a definitive criterion to halt or slow down the increase in graphical indices due to the excessive number of descriptors.

Gutman & Tošović²⁸ explored how degree descriptors might be used to identify the physical and chemical properties of isomeric octanes, which are indicative of alkanes. Malik et al.²⁹ have expanded this investigation to include the class of black holes (BHs). Hayat et al.³⁰ studied polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons (PAHs), a subgroup of BHs, and predicted their quantum-theoretic features using degree descriptors. Nikolic et al.³¹ analyse the efficiency of the sum-connectivity and Randić indices in forecasting the heat of creation for BHs. Hayat et al.³² (Hayat and colleagues³³) established the potential of distance descriptors to correlate physicochemical features, specifically the total π -electron energy E_π , of lower BHs. Chen³⁴ studied the general Randić and general sum-connectivity indices to predict the E_π of BHs. The authors

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in Redžepovic & Furtula³⁵ and ³⁶⁻³⁹ examined the correlation power of eigenvalues-based graphical indicators for physicochemical attributes and the E_π of BHs.

This research focuses solely on assessing the effectiveness of R molecular topological indices in predicting the chemical properties of BHs.

In [Figure 1](#), images symbolizing the chemical structure of the benzenoid hydrocarbons whose properties we examined are given.

Figure 1. (a) Benzene, (b) Naphthalene, (c) Phenanthrene, (d) Anthracene, (e) Chrysene, (f) Benzo[a]anthracene, (g) Triphenylene, (h) Tetracene, (i) Benzo[a]pyrene, (j) Benzo[e]pyrene, (k) Perylene, (l) Anthanthrene,

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(m) Benzo[ghi]perylene, (n) Dibenz[a,c]anthracene, (o) Dibenz[a,h]anthracene, (p) Dibenz[a,j]anthracene,
 (q) Picene, (r) Coronene, (s) Dibenzo[a,h]pyrene, (t) Dibenzo[a,i]pyrene, (u) Dibenzo[a,l]pyrene,
 (v) Pyrene⁴⁴.

The r -degree⁴⁰ of the vertex v , denoted as $r(v)$, is defined as

$$r(v) = S(v) + M(v)$$

and the inverse r -degree⁴⁰ of the vertex v , denoted as $ir(v)$, is defined as

$$ir(v) = \frac{1}{r(v)}$$

Although the author who defined the R indices⁴⁰ and indicated this index with the letter R, we prefer to indicate it with $\mathfrak{R}$ in this article because this notation causes confusion with the Randic index.

The first R index⁴⁰ of a simple connected graph G is defined as;

$$\mathfrak{R}^1(G) = \sum_{v \in V(G)} r(v)^2$$

The second R index⁴⁰ of a simple connected graph G is defined as;

$$\mathfrak{R}^2(G) = \sum_{uv \in E(G)} r(u)r(v)$$

The third R index⁴⁰ of a simple connected graph G is defined as;

$$\mathfrak{R}^3(G) = \sum_{uv \in E(G)} [r(u) + r(v)]$$

The first inverse R index⁴⁰ of a simple connected graph G is defined as;

$$\mathfrak{R}^{1i}(G) = \sum_{v \in V(G)} ir(v)^2$$

The second inverse R index⁴⁰ of a simple connected graph G is defined as;

$$\mathfrak{R}^{2i}(G) = \sum_{uv \in E(G)} ir(u)ir(v)$$

The third inverse R index⁴⁰ of a simple linked graph G is defined as;

$$\mathbb{R}^{3i}(G) = \sum_{uv \in E(G)} [ir(u) + ir(v)].$$

2. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

This section examines how R indices can be used to construct linear, quadratic and cubic regression models for various properties of benzenoid hydrocarbons, such as boiling point (BO), π -electron energy (π -ele), molecular weight (MW), polarizability (PO), molar volume (MV), and molar refractivity (MF). Table 1 displays the physical characteristics of benzenoid hydrocarbons and their calculated R indices. The parameters examined in the study have demonstrated a strong association with the specified R topological indices using regression models as referenced⁴¹⁻⁴³.

Table 1. Physical characteristics and estimated R indices.

Dervatives of Benzene	BP	π -ele	MW	PO	MV	MR	$\mathbb{R}^1$	$\mathbb{R}^2$	$\mathbb{R}^3$	$\mathbb{R}^{1i}$	$\mathbb{R}^{2i}$	$\mathbb{R}^{3i}$
Benzene	78,8	8	78,11	10,4	89,4	26,3	384	384	96	0,0938	0,0938	1,5
Naphthalene	221,5	13,683	128,17	17,5	123,5	44,1	1462	1677	266	0,1011	0,0986	2,0431
Phenanthrene	337,4	19,448	178,23	24,6	157,7	61,9	3056	3673	466	0,1206	0,1166	2,6375
Anthracene	337,4	19,314	178,23	24,6	157,7	61,9	2634	3178	440	0,1155	0,1154	2,6255
Chrysene	448	25,192	228,3	31,6	191,8	79,8	4650	5718	666	0,1401	0,1348	3,2319
Benzo[a] anthracene	436,7	25,101	228,3	31,6	191,8	79,8	4228	5202	640	0,135	0,1338	3,2199
Triphenylene	425	25,275	228,3	31,6	191,8	79,8	5166	6492	696	0,1522	0,1449	3,2832
Tetracene	436,7	25,188	228,3	31,6	191,8	79,8	3806	4679	614	0,13	0,1322	3,208
Benzo[a]pyrene	495	28,222	252,3	35,8	196,1	90,3	6773	8508	854	0,133	0,1301	3,3669
Benzo[e]pyrene	467,5	28,336	252,3	35,8	196,1	90,3	7410	9419	894	0,1368	0,1298	3,3344
Perylene	467,5	28,245	252,3	35,8	196,1	90,3	7242	9079	882	0,1416	0,3387	3,3985
Anthanthrene	497,1	31,253	276,3	40	200,4	100,8	8839	11317	1036	0,1333	0,1314	3,5701
Benzo[ghi] perylene	501	31,425	276,3	40	200,4	100,8	9318	12131	1068	0,131	0,1273	3,5139
Dibenz[a,c] anthracene	518	30,942	278,3	38,7	225,9	97,6	6338	8049	870	0,1666	0,1624	3,8657
Dibenz[a,h]anthracene	524,7	30,881	278,3	38,7	225,9	97,6	5822	7226	840	0,1545	0,1521	3,8143
Dibenz[a,j]anthracene	524,7	30,88	278,3	38,7	225,9	97,6	5822	7226	840	0,1545	0,1521	3,8143
Picene	519	30,943	278,3	38,7	225,9	97,6	6244	7763	866	0,1596	0,1531	3,8263
Coronene	525,6	34,572	300,4	44,1	204,7	111,4	11394	15114	1254	0,1204	0,1204	3,6292
Dibenzo[a,h] pyrene	552,3	33,928	302,4	42,9	230,2	108,1	8414	10718	1056	0,156	0,1532	3,981

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Dibenzo[a,i] pyrene	552,3	33,954	302,4	42,9	230,2	108,1	8414	10718	1056	0,156	0,1532	3,981
Dibenzo[a,l] pyrene	552,3	34,031	302,4	42,9	230,2	108,1	9188	11941	1093	0,1652	0,161	4,0231
Pyrene	404	22,506	202,25	28,7	162	72,5	3957	4448	577	0,1175	0,1153	2,9422

Table 2 shows the correlation coefficients calculated from the values in Table 1.

Table 2. Correlation coefficients between R indices and chemical properties of benzenoid hydrocarbons.

Property	ξ^1	ξ^2	ξ^3	ξ^{1t}	ξ^{2t}	ξ^{3t}
BP	0,8324	0,8156	0,9138	0,8234	0,3692	0,9852
π -ele	0,9104	0,8991	0,9685	0,7928	0,3615	0,9786
MW	0,8945	0,8825	0,9585	0,8121	0,3670	0,9855
PO	0,9203	0,9094	0,9743	0,7764	0,3579	0,9727
MV	0,7639	0,7485	0,8621	0,9123	0,3860	0,9936
MR	0,9203	0,9094	0,9744	0,7760	0,3579	0,9726

As can be seen in Table 2, the third inverse R index gave the highest correlation coefficient with a boiling point of 0,9852.

The graphs of the linear, quadratic, and cubic regression equations of this relationship are given in Figures 2-4.

The linear regression equation between the third inverse R index and the boiling point is

$$y = -142,6175 + 177,9987x$$

and the graph of this equation is shown in Figure 2.

Figure 2. Linear regression model of the third inverse R index with boiling point

The quadratic regression equation relating the third inverse R index to the boiling point is

$$y = -387,5747 + 358,6628x - 31,1044x^2$$

and Figure 3 displays the graph of this equation.

Figure 3. Quadratic regression model of the third inverse R index with boiling point

The cubic regression equation that connects the third inverse R index to the boiling point is

$$y = -370,2486 + 338,0887x - 23,5212x^2 - 0,8856x^3.$$

Figure 4 illustrates this equation graphically.

Figure 4. Cubic regression model for the third inverse R index in relation to boiling point

Table 2 shows that the third inverse R index had the greatest correlation coefficient of 0,9786 with a π -electron energy.

Figures 5-7 display the graphs of the linear, quadratic, and cubic regression equations for this connection.

The linear regression equation between the third inverse R index and the π -electron energy is

$$y = -7,7883 + 10,4747x$$

and the graph of this equation is shown in Figure 5.

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Figure 5. Linear regression model of the third inverse R index with π -electron energy

The quadratic regression equation relating the third inverse R index to the π -electron energy is

$$y = -9,3727 + 11,6432x - 0,2012x^2$$

and **Figure 6** displays the graph of this equation.

Figure 6. Quadratic regression model of the third inverse R index with the π -electron energy

The cubic regression equation that connects the third inverse R index to the boiling point is

$$y = 12,4676 - 15,4788x + 9,7960x^2 - 1,1674x^3.$$

Figure 7 illustrates this equation graphically.

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Figure 7. Cubic regression model for the third inverse R index in relation to the π -electron energy Table 2 shows that the third inverse R index had the greatest correlation coefficient of 0,9855 with a molecular weight. Figures 8-10 display the graphs of the linear, quadratic, and cubic regression equations for this connection.

The linear regression equation between the third inverse R index and the molecular weight is

$$y = -56,9378 + 90,1129x$$

and the graph of this equation is shown in Figure 8.

Figure 8. Linear regression model of the third inverse R index with molecular weight

The quadratic regression equation relating the third inverse R index to the molecular weight is

$$y = -69,5066 + 99,3828x - 1,5960x^2$$

and Figure 9 displays the graph of this equation.

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Figure 9. Quadratic regression model of the third inverse R index with the molecular weight

The cubic regression equation that connects the third inverse R index to the molecular weight is

$$y = 82,4265 - 81,0321x + 64,9020x^2 - 7,7654x^3.$$

Figure 10 illustrates this equation graphically.

Figure 10. Cubic regression model of the third inverse R index with the molecular weight

As can be seen in Table 2, the third R index gave the highest correlation coefficient with a polarization of 0,9743. The graphs of the linear, quadratic, and cubic regression equations of this relationship are given in Figures 11-13.

The linear regression equation between the third R index and the polarization is

$$y = 11,2086 + 0,0293x$$

and the graph of this equation is shown in Figure 11.

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Figure 11. Linear regression model of the third R index with polarization

The quadratic regression equation relating the third R index to the polarization is

$$y = 5,4703 + 0,0496x - 0,0002x^2$$

and **Figure 12** displays the graph of this equation.

Figure 12. Quadratic regression model of the third R index with the polarization

The cubic regression equation that connects the third R index to the molecular weight is

$$y = 6,1114 + 0,0450x - 7.10^{-5}x^2 - 4.10^{-8}x^3.$$

Figure 13 illustrates this equation graphically.

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Figure 13. Cubic regression model of the third inverse R index with the polarization

Table 2 shows that the third inverse R index had the greatest correlation coefficient of 0,9936 with a molecular volume.

Figures 14-16 display the graphs of the linear, quadratic, and cubic regression equations for this connection. The linear regression equation between the third inverse R index and the molecular volume is

$$y = 6,9427 + 56,2120x$$

and the graph of this equation is shown in Figure 14.

Figure 14. Linear regression model of the third inverse R index with molecular volume

The quadratic regression equation relating the third inverse R index to the molecular volume is

$$y = 4,9508 + 57,6806x - 0,2529x^2$$

and Figure 15 displays the graph of this equation.

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Figure 15. Quadratic regression model of the third inverse R index with the molecular volume

The cubic regression equation that connects the third inverse R index to the molecular volume is

$$y = -35,7521 + 106,0138x - 18,0676x^2 + 2,0804x^3.$$

Figure 16 illustrates this equation graphically.

Figure 16. Cubic regression model of the third inverse R index with the molecular volume

As can be seen in Table 2, the third R index gave the highest correlation coefficient with a molar refractivity of 0.9744.

The graphs of the linear, quadratic, and cubic regression equations of this relationship are given in Figures 17-19. The

linear regression equation between the third R index and the molar refractivity is

$$y = 28,2940 + 0,0739x$$

and the graph of this equation is shown in Figure 17.

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Figure 17. Linear regression model of the third R index with molar refractivity

The quadratic regression equation relating the third R index to the molar refractivity is

$$y = 13,8163 + 0,1252x - 4.10^{-5}x^2$$

and **Figure 18** displays the graph of this equation.

Figure 18. Quadratic regression model of the third R index with molar refractivity

The cubic regression equation relating the third R index to the molar refractivity is

$$y = 15,3543 + 0,1140x - 2.10^{-5}x^2 - 1.10^{-8}x^3$$

and **Figure 19** displays the graph of this equation.

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Figure 19. Quadratic regression model of the third R index with molar refractivity

3. CONCLUSION

This article focuses on modelling some chemical properties of benzenoid hydrocarbons of R molecular topological indices. The R molecular indices demonstrate potential usefulness in several domains and are gaining popularity. Regression models are employed to verify this, and statistical parameters are calculated. Based on this data, the indicator is deemed to be possibly predictive. Curvilinear regression models are used to assess the chemical applicability of benzenoid hydrocarbons, employing linear, quadratic, and cubic equations. All models have demonstrated encouraging results in terms of the statistical parameters analysed. The third inverse R index is identified as the most promising predictive index for the boiling point, π -electron energy, molecular weight, and molar volume of benzenoid hydrocarbons, as determined by the study utilizing curvilinear models. Also, the third R index is identified as the most promising predictive index for molar refractivity and polarization. Graphical representations of the linear, quadratic, and cubic models for each physicochemical property analysed in the study are displayed in Figure 2-19. The plots displays the variation of each model for each property in relation to the third R indices. This study on topological indices in chemistry, particularly in drug design and development, may be beneficial for researchers interested in exploring indices for different chemical compounds and medications.

Conflict of interest

The author declares that there is no a conflict of interest.

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